

ART FRONTIER

An International Art Journal / Vol. 3, No. 2 (Total Issue No. 10) Apr.-Jun., 2025

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To cite this article: Jingwei Zeng, "Between Ink and Illumination: Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* in a Global Horizon," *Art Frontier* 3, no.2 (June 2025): 9-24, <https://doi.org/10.64212/VFJQ2993>.

DOI: 10.64212/VFJQ2993

ISSN: 2835-5490

EISSN: 2836-841X

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This article has undergone double-blind peer review.

Website: www.artfrontier.org

Email: artfrontier2023@outlook.com

Publishing Frequency: Quarterly (March, June, September, December)

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Jingwei Zeng

Abstract

This essay examines Lixiang Zhang's (張立翔) *Chengxiang* (澄象, Purified Image) series as a pivotal case for understanding how contemporary Chinese ink painting redefines abstraction within global modernism. Through comparative dialogue with Mark Rothko and Isamu Noguchi, it argues that Zhang's art transcends binary distinctions between East and West, tradition and modernity, materiality and transcendence. Drawing on Zong Bing's (宗炳) theory of *chenghuai weixiang* ("purify the mind and savor images"), the study situates Zhang's practice within a continuum that unites Daoist-Buddhist meditation and modern abstraction. While Rothko's color fields express the existential sublime and Noguchi's sculptures transform landscape into spiritual space, Zhang's ink paintings internalize both impulses—transforming the dialectic of void and form into a contemplative field of illumination. His work demonstrates that abstraction is not the monopoly of Western modernism but a shared visual language through which diverse traditions seek spiritual clarity and inward stillness.

Key Words

Lixiang Zhang, *Chengxiang*, Mark Rothko, Isamu Noguchi, global ink art

Introduction

The question of how contemporary Chinese ink painting should be positioned within the global history of art has long been both central and contentious. Over the past two decades, cultural hybridity has become a defining feature of the twentieth- and twenty-first-century Asian art experience. A telling example is the Metropolitan Museum of Art's 2013 exhibition *Ink Art: Past as Present in Contemporary China* (December 11, 2013–April 6, 2014). As stated in the exhibition overview, "the exhibition features artworks that may best be understood as part of the continuum of China's traditional culture. These works may also be appreciated from the perspective of global art, but by examining them through the lens of Chinese historical artistic paradigms, layers of meaning and cultural significance that might otherwise go unnoticed are revealed."¹

This curatorial statement itself reveals the double bind faced by contemporary ink art: it is often either

absorbed into the narrative of Western abstraction, becoming a "belated modernism," or confined within the framework of cultural heritage, reduced to a representation of tradition. Against this tension, Lixiang Zhang (b. 1971) and his *Chengxiang* ("Purified Image," figure 1) series stand out as a particularly significant case—one that neither replicates the past nor merely imitates the West, but meditates upon both.

At the same time, the force of tradition remains inseparable from the vitality of contemporary art. As Robert Thorp and Richard Vinograd observes, "The strenuousness with which many contemporary artists confront the weight of tradition reveals the centrality of this issue to the full history of twentieth-century Chinese art."² Zhang's paintings—characterized by quiet expanses, restrained gestures, and meditative atmospheres—have often been described in terms of emptiness (虛) and clarity (澄), the quintessential characteristics of Chinese tradition. Rooted in the material sensibility of tradition, his practice resists both

Figure 1. Lixiang Zhang. *Chengxiang* (from the “*Chengxiang*” series). Painting, Ink on paper, 70.87×76.38in (180×194cm), 2024.

figurative representation and overt conceptualism. Instead, the *Chengxiang* works foreground what Zhang himself calls “a clarity of image beyond image,” a liminal state where form dissolves into presence.

Crucially, the very term “Chengxiang Ink” (Chengxiang Shuimo) was first proposed by the contemporary art critic and curator Jia Tingfeng, who also bestowed the name upon Zhang’s practice. As Jia explains, “*Chengxiang* means the continual process of uncovering the essence of art and the authenticity of things through persistent artistic cultivation and practice. It stresses the importance of deeply engaging with the finest traditions of Chinese art while also studying outstanding works of world art, using innovative contemporary forms to

reinterpret the Chinese tradition and to continually broaden the boundaries of artistic understanding.” This articulation not only gave Zhang’s artistic vision its defining name but also provided a theoretical foundation that bridges art criticism and creative praxis. By integrating Jia’s philosophical insight into his own meditative methodology, Zhang transformed ‘Chengxiang Ink’ into both a visual and moral pursuit—one that aspires to clarity through continual refinement and spiritual awakening.

Such an aesthetic raises several critical questions: Is this abstraction in the Western modernist sense, or a continuation of Chinese literati philosophy? How might we frame Zhang’s *Chengxiang* paintings without

collapsing them into either pole of global modernity or national tradition? These questions point to a broader concern within global abstraction: the search for a shared yet pluralistic visual language capable of expressing inwardness, spirituality, and universality.

This article addresses these questions by placing Zhang in dialogue with two seemingly disparate figures: Mark Rothko (1903–1970), a leading voice of Abstract Expressionism, and Isamu Noguchi (1904–1988), the Japanese American sculptor and designer. At first glance, Rothko and Noguchi appear to occupy divergent domains—painting and sculpture, the gallery and the landscape—but both engage deeply with the phenomenology of perception, the construction of contemplative environments, and the mediation between material minimalism and spiritual intensity. By juxtaposing Rothko's "abstract sublime" with Noguchi's spatial poetics—from the early *Play Mountain* to the sacred landscape of Kūkaniloko—this study situates Zhang's *Chengxiang* paintings at the intersection of color and space, emotion and stillness, matter and mind.

Methodologically, this study draws upon comparative aesthetics and global art history. It resists both a diffusionist model (which would regard Zhang as belatedly echoing Western modernism) and a culturalist model (which would limit his work to the category of "Chinese ink art"). Instead, it proposes to read *Chengxiang* as part of a transnational dialogue in which

distinct strategies of abstraction and spatial experience converge on a shared inquiry: How can art generate states of contemplative presence in an age of global modernity?

The discussion proceeds in three stages. Part I situates Zhang's *Chengxiang* series within the intellectual and aesthetic lineage of Chinese landscape theory, tracing its philosophical roots in Zong Bing's (宗炳) concept of "澄懷味象 (purify the mind and savor images)" and in Zhang's own formative experiences. Part II turns to Mark Rothko, examining how his color fields and their reception within the discourse of the "abstract sublime" illuminate Zhang's use of ink, void, and tonal gradation. Part III turns to Isamu Noguchi's spatial aesthetics—particularly his *Play Mountain* and his design for the sacred Hawaiian site Kūkaniloko—highlighting his strategies of minimal intervention and contemplative space.

Together, these comparisons position Zhang's *Chengxiang* as a negotiation between image and space, materiality and transcendence. Ultimately, this paper argues that Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* paintings should not be read as peripheral to either Chinese or Western traditions but as articulating a distinctive mode of abstraction that reimagines painting as sacred space. In doing so, Zhang extends both the literati legacy of ink as a medium of reflection and the modernist pursuit of the sublime into a new field of cross-cultural resonance

Figure 2. Lixiang Zhang. *Chengxiang* (from the "*Chengxiang*" series). Painting, Ink on paper, 37.80×70.87in (96×180cm), 2024.

and spiritual depth.

1. The Artistic Context of Zhang Lixiang's Chengxiang and Spiritual Luminescence

Lixiang Zhang, currently the Dean of the School of Fine Arts and Design at Daqing Normal University, is a Professor and Graduate Advisor. His *Chengxiang* (figure 2) series must be understood as a contemporary articulation that traverses both tradition and modernity. The very term *Chengxiang* (literally “purification of image”) carries rich philosophical connotations: it echoes the Daoist notion of “clarifying the mind to perceive the Way” (*chenghuai guandao* 澄懷觀道) and resonates with traditional aesthetic concepts such as *yixiang* (artistic image) and *qiyun* (spiritual resonance). Zhang is not merely perpetuating the conventions of ink painting; rather, he transforms abstraction into a mode of spiritual cultivation, endowing contemporary art with a renewed meditative dimension.

The term *Chengxiang* originates from Zong Bing's 宗炳 (375–443) seminal essay *A Preface to the Painting of Landscapes* (*Hua shanshui xu* 《畫山水序》), which begins with the statement: “聖人含道應物，賢者澄懷味象” (“The sage encompasses the Dao and responds to things; worthies purify their minds and savor images”).³ This concept of “image” (*xiang*) derives from Zong Bing's teacher, the eminent Buddhist patriarch Huiyuan (慧遠, 334–416). In Huiyuan's *Inscription for a Buddhist Image*, the “image” is described in mystical terms:

“Broad is the great image, its patterns mysterious and nameless. When the body's spirit begins its transformation, it sheds its shadow and leaves its form. Circling in the radiance over the layered precipice, it congeals onto an empty pavilion. In the shade, it is not darkened, and in the dark, light intrudes. Stepping delicately, it molts from its shell, and pays respect to the hundred spirits. Responding in a different mode, its traces vanish and grow dark.”⁴

“廓矣大象。理玄無名。體神入化。落影離形。迴輝層岩。凝映虛亭。在陰不昧。處暗逾明。婉步蟬蛻。朝宗百靈。應不同方。跡絕而冥。”⁵

According to Zong-qi Cai and Stephen Roddy, this “image” is “converting Buddha into an eternal deity or spirit who takes form amidst the myriad things yet also exists in a state that transcends physical form.”⁶ In other words, the visible form becomes a vehicle of the invisible, linking the image of nature and the image of Buddha as manifestations of the same cosmic truth.⁷ In the fourth section of *A Preface to the Painting of Landscapes*, Zong Bing elaborates on this higher

dimension of transcendence—namely, “the transcendence of the spirit to find the truth.” He writes:

“The [transcendent] principle in landscape is what we respond to with the eye and meet with the mind. If a painting has deftly achieved correspondence with a landscape, we can engage it with eye and mind in the same fashion. Through such a response, one communes with the spirit, achieves a transcendence of one's own spirit, and attains the [absolute] principle. Even though one can again search for the invisible amongst remote rocks, what else can be found? Infinite as it is by nature, the spirit dwells in forms and resonates with things by category, to the effect that the [transcendent] principle enters even reflections and traces. If a painting is executed to truly marvelous effect, the same will surely occur in it.”⁸

“夫以應目會心為理者，類之成巧，則目亦同應，心亦俱會。應會感神，神超理得。雖複虛求幽岩，何以加焉？又神本亡端，棲形感類，理入影跡，誠能妙寫，亦誠盡矣。”⁹

From the beginning of this passage, Zong Bing emphasizes the combination of subjective perception (“respond to with the eye”) and objective mental engagement (“meet with the mind”). Only when these two are harmonized can painting achieve its highest, transcendent effect.

This spiritual luminescence is further articulated in the fifth section of the Preface:

“Therefore, I live a leisurely life, controlling my vital breath, waving my cup, and strumming my lute. As I unroll paintings and face them in solitude, I probe far into the four desolate corners, not avoiding the overgrowth at the world's fringes, and confront the uninhabited wilderness by myself. The peaks and grottoes soar high, and the cloudy forests stretch deep into the distance. The sages and worthies cast their reflections from time immemorial, and the myriad things of interest are infused with their spirit and thought. What then should I do? Nothing but let my spirit expand untrammelled. Speaking of the expansion of one's spirit, how could there be an order of who was before whom?”¹⁰

“於是閒居理氣，拂觴鳴琴，披圖幽對，坐究四荒，不違天勵之叢，獨應無人之野。峰岫嶢嶷，雲林森眇。聖賢暎於絕代，萬趣融其神思。餘複何為哉？暢神而已。神之所暢，孰有先焉！”¹¹

Here Zong Bing uses the Buddhist notions of *shen* (神, “spirit”) and *chang shen* (暢神, “to let my spirit expand untrammelled”) to express the highest standard of landscape painting. It “conveys the sense of a sagely radiance actively shining on, penetrating into, and eventually transforming myriad things into embodiments of the divine spirit.”¹²

By invoking this lineage of spiritual radiance, Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* may be read as both a continuation and a transformation of Zong Bing's vision—translating the metaphysical ideals of purification and illumination into a visual language

Figure 3. Lixiang Zhang. *Chengxiang* (from the “*Chengxiang*” series). Painting, Ink on paper, 37.80×77.95in (96×198cm), 2023.

Figure 4. Caspar David Friedrich (1774-1840), *Monk by the Sea*. Oil on canvas, 110×171.5cm, 1808-1810. Post 2015 restoration. Inv.: NG 9/85. PHOTO CREDIT: bpk Bildagentur/ (Museum: Nationalgalerie/Staatliche Museen/Berlin/Germany) / (Photographer: Andres Kilger) / Art Resource, NY. ASSET IMAGE NUMBER: ART517192. ASSET SOURCE NUMBER: 70139122.

of contemporary abstraction. Through this dialogue between ancient thought and modern form, Zhang renders the Buddhist “spiritual luminescence” tangible

in ink and space. In this sense, *Chengxiang* not only inherits the contemplative core of literati painting but also extends it into the domain of modern abstraction,

where spirit and form once again converge.

Indeed, Chinese pictorial art has long functioned as a vehicle for transmitting philosophical and social motives.¹³ Where Zong Bing spoke of the spirit's transcendence, Zhang materializes that vision through ink, brush, and space, turning metaphysical speculation into perceptual experience.

Formally, the *Chengxiang* series expands the boundaries of traditional ink painting. Zhang often employs large-scale rice paper, where washes of ink diffuse layer by layer, generating a profound sense of spatial depth while preserving the fluidity of the medium (figure 3). His works are non-representational, relying on the interplay between ink and void to create spaces that are simultaneously ambiguous and lucid. In such spaces, the viewer's perception is guided toward contemplation and stillness, as though encountering not merely an image but an inner manifestation of spirit.

At first glance, one observes a delicate architecture of lines delineating mountain ridges—each stroke ascending in measured rhythm—while around them, layers of clouds unfold in heavy yet vital undulations. The composition is simultaneously precise and spontaneous, rough yet spirited. This evokes the sublime solitude of Caspar David Friedrich's (1774–1840) *Monk Before the Sea* (1808–1810, figure 4), which evokes a strong sense of solitude and the infinite.¹⁴ Celebrated as a key work of German Romanticism, Friedrich's painting explores the relationship between humankind and the sublime natural world—the tension between the finite self and boundless infinity.

Yet what Friedrich externalized in the infinite horizon, Zhang internalizes through the metaphysical language of ink. The vast expanse of sea and sky in Friedrich's painting becomes, in Zhang's *Chengxiang*, the interplay of ink and void—a contemplative field where emptiness is not absence but revelation. The idea of void or emptiness as meaningful space thus connects Friedrich's Romantic search for the infinite with Chinese painting's long-standing use of blankness, pause, and ink-wash voids.¹⁵ In addition, in the monk's resolute figure, we also “find a source of spiritual strength, defiance even... perhaps a symbol of the resolve of the nation against foreign military rule, as of the individual faced with his mortality.”¹⁶ In Zhang's solitary forms of mountain and mist, that same strength of spirit endures—quiet, meditative, and luminous—transforming the Romantic sublime into an inward, timeless contemplation.

While Friedrich's solitary monk confronts the infinite horizon as an external sublime, Zhang's *Chengxiang* turns that encounter inward. The vast space of the sky

becomes the interior void of ink and breath, where form and emptiness oscillate in spiritual dialogue. In this transformation, the landscape ceases to depict nature and instead becomes a manifestation of consciousness itself. Through this transposition of the sublime into the metaphysical, Zhang redefines abstraction as a path toward inner illumination—a vision in which the brush does not merely describe the world but reveals the quiet radiance of the mind that beholds it.

In *Chengxiang*, the dialectics of hardness and softness, square and round, sharp and blunt, weight and weightlessness, refinement and roughness become an attempted reconciliation of immanence and transcendence. It is precisely through this coexistence of contrasts that Zhang's paintings acquire their cultural richness. Such multiplicity is not confusion but openness—a visual manifestation of harmony through difference, echoing both Daoist balance and modern phenomenology.

This spiritual openness reflects Zhang's own life experience. As Clement Greenberg wrote, “Art is a matter strictly of experience, not of principles.”¹⁷ Zhang recalls:

“After graduation, I worked for eleven years in the labor union of the Daqing Petroleum Logging Company. During that time, I painted slogans and propaganda murals with broad brushes, an experience that sowed the seeds for my later transformation in Chinese painting. I flattened brushes of various sizes, breaking away from the traditional centered-tip (*zhongfeng*) form of the brush, and used light ink and dry strokes in layered sweeps to depict the snowy landscapes of the northern winter—creating a desolate, solitary, and vast sense of landscape. It was through this continual process of self-transcendence that I developed what I call the ‘Qifeng Brush Method.’ The term Qifeng literally means ‘aligned brush tips,’ referring to a disciplined brush technique in which each stroke is arranged in a systematic and unified direction, forming clusters that accumulate into an organic totality of movement and rhythm. This method, at once structural and meditative, became the technical and philosophical foundation for his later *Chengxiang* paintings.”¹⁸

Zhang also notes:

“Beginning in 2015, on the foundation of the ‘Qifeng Brush Method,’ I initiated the creation of the *Chengxiang* series. My aim was to analyze and explore the underlying logic of *Chengxiang Ink Painting*—to construct a central pictorial schema of ‘mountain of ins surging and clouds opening’ (*shanyong yunkai* 山湧雲開). Through the visual and philosophical interplay of central aggregation and diffusion, and by employing tonal gradations of ink and digital modulation within a grayscale spatial field, I sought to excavate the spiritual reflections and moral resonances embodied in *Chengxiang Ink Painting*. The term ‘Chengxiang’ itself implies observing phenomena with a clear and purified heart, transcending appearances to perceive the inner Dao, and achieving the fusion of subject and object. Through digitally modulated transitions of ink tones, gradated spaces of gray, and layered depths,

I guide the viewer's gaze beyond the visible—toward the 'image beyond the image' (xiang wai zhi xiang 象外之象)—thus attaining a limpid realm where 'distant mountains appear like indigo, and empty waters merge in mist.' ”¹⁹

Georges Duthuit, in *Chinese Mysticism and Modern Painting*, claimed that art was “a means of communion with the universe as a whole. (The artist) seeks to control the mass of the forces which rule the earth, the heavens and his own consciousness.”²⁰ Chinese art, he adds, is inspired by “speculations so transcendental, mystical and metaphysical.”²¹

Zhang echoes this insight in his own words:

“The subtle gray tones (gaoji hui 高級灰) produced by light ink on raw xuan paper—gentle, elegant, and ethereal—have always fascinated me. They form the very tonal foundation of *Chengxiang Ink Painting*. Within the gradient and layered scales of gray, I seek the critical threshold between hardness and softness, ultimately completing a leap from technique (jifa) to mind-method (xinfu). This creative paradigm not only expands the boundaries of contemporary ink art but also offers a personal model for the digital-age transformation of traditional art.”²²

In this synthesis of vision and method, Zhang fulfills the continuum that runs from Huiyuan's mystic “image,” through Zong Bing's “spiritual radiance,” to the abstract consciousness of modernity. By grounding his practice in both philosophical lineage and lived experience, Zhang turns ink painting into a space where the visible and invisible, the ancient and contemporary, converge in luminous harmony.

2. Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* and Mark Rothko — Abstraction, Spirit, and the Question of Transcendence

In dialogue with Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* series is the abstraction of Mark Rothko, whose color-field paintings of the mid-twentieth century represent one of the most profound explorations of spirituality in modern Western art. Although separated by culture, geography, and medium, both artists share a desire to embody the ineffable—the motion of spirit through light, space, and form.

The connection between abstraction and spirituality was redefined in the twentieth century amid the rise of Theosophy, which sought to reconcile Western metaphysics with Eastern spiritual traditions.²³ Within this context, Rothko's art reoriented the Western sublime from an external vision of transcendence toward an inward emotional abyss.

Rothko's canvases are typically monumental in scale, composed of vast, floating rectangles of color. The physicality of the paint creates a sensuousness that

invites deep engagement; “the viewer reacts to the vastness of the paintings that impart a sense of infinity.”²⁴ Yet these forms are never inert geometry—they seem to hover, tremble, and breathe, creating a field of radiant intensity that draws the viewer into its depths. As Robert Rosenblum famously observed, Rothko's works embody an “Abstract Sublime,”²⁵ in which form dissolves and the viewer is enveloped in pure color and light.

Rina Arya indicates that “Rothko presents an interesting case as his work can be understood as spiritual in a broadly numinous way with recourse to the concepts of the sublime and the mystical as well as reflecting aspects of his Jewish identity.”²⁶ The artist himself acknowledged this dimension of direct emotional communion:

“The fact that lots of people break down and cry when confronted with my pictures shows that I communicate those basic human emotions. The people who weep before my pictures are having the same religious experience I had when I painted them.”²⁷

According to Rina Arya, in Rothko's paintings “the viewer becomes the Rückenfigur who is situated on the edge of the abyss and encounters the vastness, infinity, magnificence, and vacuity of the colored vistas, thus giving rise to the experience of the sublime.”²⁸ Standing before Rothko's canvases, the viewer is both spectator and participant—absorbed into a field of color that feels limitless, transcendent, and deeply human (figure 5).

Rothko's abstraction, however, remains grounded in the Western intellectual lineage of the sublime. Continuing Kant's notion of the self-overwhelmed by the infinite, his paintings enact a confrontation with immensity—a radiant void in which identity dissolves. They construct what critics have called a “theater of stillness,”²⁹ where silence and scale merge into an atmosphere of quasi-religious intensity. This experience expresses not only the universal human yearning for transcendence but also the existential unease of postwar Western society.³⁰ His 1950s paintings, hailed as part of the “triumph of American painting,” brought the postwar avant-garde to prominence, framed ideologically as embodiments of democratic freedom and timeless, “universal” emotion.

In this sense, Rothko's canvases were not mere images but environments—emotional architectures that enveloped the viewer in an experience of presence and dissolution. His color fields were sanctuaries of the modern spirit.

Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* series operates within a parallel yet distinct metaphysical register. Like Rothko, Zhang employs abstraction to evoke transcendence—the dissolution of form through void and diffusion—but his

Figure 5. Mark Rothko (1903-1970) © ARS, NY. *White Center*. Painting, Oil on canvas, 84×72in (213.36×182.88cm), 1957. David E. Bright Bequest (M.67.25.21). Photo Credit: Digital Image © [2025] Museum Associates / Los Angeles County Museum of Art/Los Angeles/California/USA. Licensed by Art Resource, NY. ASSET IMAGE NUMBER: ART398230.ASSET SOURCE NUMBER: M.67.25.21.

Figure 6. Lixiang Zhang. *Chengxiang* (from the “*Chengxiang*” series). Painting, Ink and acrylic on paper, 70.87×75.98in (180×193cm), 2025.

sensibility leads toward balance rather than rupture, stillness rather than awe. Zhang’s large-scale works envelop the viewer not through the gravity of pigment but through the transparency of ink. They open a contemplative space where the eye drifts gently between tone and blankness, between motion and repose.

The use of monumental formats in *Chengxiang* thus performs a dual function. On one hand, it commands the viewer’s attention, evoking the bodily immediacy and intimacy that Rothko achieved through scale. On the other, it invites quiet immersion—an experience of interior spaciousness rather than outward vastness. The energy of Zhang’s brushwork unfolds as rhythmic breathing: his compositions expand and contract,

flickering between fullness and emptiness. Through this oscillation, space becomes a living organism, echoing Zong Bing’s ideal of *chang shen* (暢神), the spiritual expansion of the heart.

Unlike Rothko’s reliance on the emotional density of color, Zhang’s abstraction depends on diffusion and translucency. The interplay between ink and void produces a space that is simultaneously ambiguous and lucid, solid yet open. The viewer does not face the overwhelming immensity of Rothko’s sublime, but rather the Daoist serenity of “clarifying the mind” (*chenghuai* 澄懷)—a state of inward transparency (figure 6). Rothko’s sublimity dissolves the self in light, while Zhang’s *Chengxiang* clarifies the self through stillness

and resonance. Both transcend representation, but they guide the spectator along divergent paths: Rothko toward existential confrontation, Zhang toward contemplative illumination.

This inward illumination in Zhang's paintings also recalls the spiritual cosmology of ancient Chinese art. The rhythmic strata of his clouds and mountains evoke, almost subconsciously, the archetypal vision of Qiu Ying (1494-1552)'s *Portrait of Fuxi* (《伏羲像》) preserved in the National Palace Museum in Taipei. As a primordial cultural hero in Chinese mythology, Fuxi was venerated as the progenitor of civilization—he is said to have drawn the Eight Trigrams, instituted marriage, nurtured domestic animals, and brought forth music, ritual, and moral order. The mythic image of Fuxi thus symbolizes the genesis of cosmic harmony and human culture. In Zhang's visual language, this ancestral imagery is not directly depicted but internally reimagined: his layered clouds and ascending peaks become metaphors for the same creative breath that links Heaven and Earth. The spirit of Fuxi—creative, ordering, and originative—quietly resonates through Zhang's *Chengxiang*, transforming the natural landscape into a site of cultural remembrance and metaphysical renewal.

Thus, *Chengxiang* stands not only as a response to the modern dilemma of abstraction in China but also as a vital intervention in the global discourse on spirituality in art. Rather than treating abstraction as a stylistic form or an aesthetic category imported from the West, Zhang redefines it as a moral and ontological practice—a process of “self-clarification” through ink, breath, and rhythm. His paintings reveal that abstraction is not a singular, universal grammar, but a constellation of spiritual inquiries: Rothko's rooted in the trembling depths of color and emotion, and Zhang's grounded in the meditative discipline of brush and void, in which perception itself becomes ethical. In this sense, *Chengxiang* does not merely bridge East and West; it restores abstraction to its primordial function—as an act of illumination through which art becomes a vehicle for understanding the invisible order of being.

Zhang's reflections on his process reveal this philosophy in action:

“I control the number of ink drops, the ratio of water to ink. For example, when I paint a layer, I add two drops of ink; for the next layer, two more. The drop is fixed, almost like a device—it ensures precision.”³¹

This precision, however, is not mechanical but meditative. “The beauty of gradation lies in its restraint,” Zhang explains. “In the gray tones one can express the richest variations. This richness is not from contrast or loudness, nor from vast spatial expansion, but from

subtle transitions within narrow limits. The gradation of ink is a silent symphony of color.” He continues: “Through the delicate layering of light ink, I seek a realm where ‘five shades of ink’ embody the infinite richness of the world—where in the simplest hue, the deepest spiritual world becomes visible.”

Such discipline reflects not only aesthetic rigor but moral order. Each gradation, Zhang notes, must proceed step by step—slightly darker, slightly lighter—as though climbing a staircase. This sense of proportion reflects an inner lawfulness, a self-regulating harmony that mirrors the cosmic order.

This devotion to subtle control recalls Rothko's own calibrated mastery of hue and saturation. As E.-M. Papia and A. Kondi observe, his color fields “were not simply visual constructs but carefully calibrated expressions of artistic intent.”³² Both artists transform restraint into revelation, demonstrating that precision itself can be a mode of transcendence.

Yet Zhang remains cautious about the pitfalls of decorative abstraction, echoing the warning that “only when it becomes mere decoration does abstract art proceed in a void and truly turn into ‘dehumanized’ art.”³³ For him, ink is never ornament but a moral and spiritual medium—the disciplined vehicle of illumination.

If Rothko's radiance embodies the trembling vastness of existence, Zhang's gradations of gray reveal the steady pulse of the Dao. Through the simplest of materials—water, ink, and paper—he reaches toward the same horizon of transcendence that Rothko sought through color and light, affirming that spiritual abstraction, whether Western or Eastern, is at its heart a dialogue between the visible and the unseen.

3. Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* and Isamu Noguchi—Nature, Space, and the Return of the Mind

Unlike Mark Rothko's abstraction, which centers on the sublime experience of color, the art of Isamu Noguchi—a Japanese American sculptor and designer—focuses on the dialogue between human beings, nature, and space. For Noguchi, sculpture was never confined to the object: it was a way of reshaping the relationship between matter, space, and the human presence within the world.³⁴

In the 1970s, Noguchi proposed a design for the sacred Hawaiian site Kūkaniloko, where he envisioned surrounding the ancient birthstones with grass berms (figure 7). His intention was not to impose a new form but to create a minimal intervention—an act of

Figure 7. Isamu Noguchi, *Model for Sacred Rocks of Kukaniloko*. Foam core, Styrofoam, plaster, paint. 2×24×23 3/4in (5.1×61×60.3cm), 1976. Collection of the Isamu Noguchi Foundation and Garden Museum, New York. The Noguchi Museum Archives, 00804. Photo: Kevin Noble. © The Isamu Noguchi Foundation and Garden Museum, New York / Artists Rights Society (ARS), New York.

protection that shielded the site from nearby pineapple fields and roads.³⁵ In doing so, he transformed the landscape into a contemplative environment in which visitors could focus on the stones' spiritual significance. Here, sculpture became space, and space became meditation. Noguchi's art was less about sculptural form than about shaping an immersive spiritual environment that invited participation and stillness.

The spatial mediation in this context resonates deeply with Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* series. Zhang's ink paintings often deploy vast fields of blankness (void) and translucent washes to construct what may be called a "field of the mind (figure 8)." Facing these works, the viewer experiences a spatial paradox: expansiveness that feels infinite yet inwardness that feels personal. Much like Noguchi's interventions, Zhang's paintings rely not on visual complexity but on purification and clarity,

producing a space that can be "inhabited" by the spirit rather than by the body.

Both Noguchi and Zhang, in different ways, transform space into an instrument of mindfulness. Yet their shared aesthetic also embodies a deeper history of displacement and transformation. As scholars have noted, Noguchi's career continually wrestled with "how identities might (or might not) be negotiated and positioned within the racialized cultural matrix of the United States after Pearl Harbor."³⁶ His art reflects the search for belonging amid dislocation—a condition that, in his words, demanded "a way of life, a space of life... a world that exists, grows, and changes from its own force."³⁷

Zhang's background, though distinct, also carries the marks of transformation and endurance. His parents immigrated to Daqing in 1962, three years after the fou-

Figure 8. Lixiang Zhang. *Chengxiang* (from the “*Chengxiang*” series). Painting, Ink on paper, 67.72×67.72in (172×172cm), 2025.

ending of the city, to contribute to the development of the oil field, and he grew up within an environment materially shaped by this national enterprise. From 1964 to 1980, the Daqing Oil Field contributed more than 50 percent of China’s annual crude oil production, and by the end of the 1970s “China had already transformed itself from an oil importer to an oil exporter.”³⁸ Yet life in Daqing remained defined by perseverance: the oil workers toiled in open fields, rain or snow, drilling year-round.

Zhang still recalls the poems of the “Iron Man” generation, verses that embody both physical struggle

and spiritual fortitude:

When oil workers give a mighty roar,
Even the earth trembles three times more.
With boundless drive and courage vast,
No hardship under heaven can hold them fast.

— Wang Jinxi

The north wind serves as an electric fan,
And snow as dry flour in our pan.
From north and south, we join the fight,
To claim the nation’s top oil site.

Work! Work! Work!

— Wang Jinxi

Among the rows of standards, another rises tall,
Steel men emerge from the Iron Man's call.
Who are these men of tempered might?
We answer proudly—we are the light!

— Anonymous

Wang Jinxi (1923–1970), known as “Iron Man Wang,” was the legendary leader of the Daqing Oil Field workers and a national symbol of resilience and collective will.³⁹ Renowned for his unyielding dedication—famously mixing drilling mud with his own body when equipment failed—he personified the Daqing Spirit (Daqing jingshen 大慶精神): perseverance, innovation, and self-reliance. For Zhang, who grew up in Daqing, this spirit was not propaganda but lived experience. The ethos of courage in adversity became internalized as artistic conviction. His surging mountains and dissolving mists recall the same moral vigor and fortitude celebrated in Wang's poetry—a vital energy that fuses labor, nature, and the indomitable human will.

This moral and material continuity between labor and creation finds a striking visual embodiment in Zhang's triptych *Unrecorded Memory* (《未知的銘記》, figure 9). The work presents a vast expanse of black, layered like fertile soil strata, ascending toward a narrow band of white at the top. Within the darkness, the faint outlines of drilling machinery emerge—an unmistakable allusion to the Daqing oil fields where Zhang once lived and worked. Unlike the ethereal diffusion of his later *Chengxiang* pieces, here the “gravity of pigment” asserts itself with palpable density and weight, recalling Rothko's somber chromatic fields. Yet beneath this heaviness lies a profound meditation on endurance and regeneration: the black earth becomes both matter and metaphor, a site where memory, labor, and artistic creation converge. In transforming the industrial landscape of his youth into a metaphysical terrain, Zhang reclaims the toil of the oil field as an act of spiritual excavation—a search for meaning buried within the layers of lived history.

Zhang often reflects that “the power of human beings lies in the ability to let the mountains (the self) rise and the clouds (external disturbance) part.” For him, true strength is internal clarity—the *chengming* (證明) of the mind that perceives the laws of the cosmos. His studio, named “Cangdan Tang (Hall of Hiding the Gall, 藏膽堂),” embodies this philosophy: perseverance, courage, and spiritual resilience. Equally formative were his later experiences: in 2005 he studied in the Advanced Seminar on Contemporary Art Criticism and Writing led by Professor Yi Ying at the Central Academy of Fine Arts, which deepened his fascination with the theoretical foundations of contemporary ink art; between 2009 and

2013 he followed the development of Taihe Art Space and its founder Jia Tingfeng, whose curatorial vision profoundly shaped his understanding of experimental ink; and in 2016 he entered the Hubei Institute of Fine Arts in Wuhan—China's major center for contemporary art—to pursue a master's degree under Professor Xu Yongmin, whose guidance in both scholarship and studio practice refined Zhang's perspective to connect East and West. Like drilling for oil beneath a complex crust, painting becomes for Zhang an act of exploration—unveiling the unknown depths of existence.

Noguchi, too, consistently sought a union of art and life through nature. In his garden and landscape designs, “he managed to transform the utopian social character and industrial-age anonymity of the Constructivist monument—and its Minimalist corporate equivalent today—into an essentially intimate and reflective experience.”⁴⁰ As Dakin Hart notes, Noguchi's understanding of space was “experiential rather than didactic, branching and connective rather than socially prescriptive,” achieving a “layered, shifting, and purposefully irresolvable wholeness.”⁴¹

One of the earliest manifestations of this philosophy was *Play Mountain* (1934, figure 10), a 25-inch plaster model for an unrealized playground in midtown Manhattan. The design featured a pyramid-like mound with carved slopes, steps, and curved forms, allowing children to run, climb, and slide directly on the sculpted earth.⁴² It was one of the first attempts to dissolve the boundary between fine art and everyday life, transforming sculpture into lived experience.

The ridged sides of *Play Mountain*—layered lines ascending in rhythmic strata—recall Zhang's *Qifeng* (齊峰) brushwork, where lines accumulate like mountain ridges, one atop another (figure 11). Both artists, through their respective media, pursue an organic geometry that unites discipline with spontaneity, structure with vitality. Zhang's paintings, like Noguchi's earthworks, are meditations on the relationship between order and freedom, matter and emptiness.

Zhang himself has said:

“I hope Chengxiang Ink Painting, with its clear and transparent qualities, can open a spiritual sanctuary and a tranquil aesthetic pursuit. By controlling the ratio of water to ink, the surface acquires a sense of ethereality and depth. This seemingly mechanical precision is, in fact, a conscious balance between freedom and restraint, leading viewers into a purified meditative space. Through the delicate gradation of ink tones, I construct paths of spiritual exploration. The motif of ‘Mountains Surging and Clouds Opening’ (Shanyong yunkai) embodies multiple spiritual dimensions... How can one find a resting place for the spirit? Chengxiang offers an answer—through inner calm and steadfastness, transforming the literati's ‘viewing of things to grasp their essence’

Figure 9. Lixiang Zhang. *Unrecorded Memory*. Triptych, Ink on paper, 51.97×25.98in×3 (132×66cm×3), 2025.

Figure 10. Isamu Noguchi, *Play Mountain*. Bronze. 3 3/8×25 1/4×28 3/4in (8.6×64.1×73cm), 1933. Collection of The Isamu Noguchi Foundation and Garden Museum, New York. The Noguchi Museum Archives, 00023. Photo: Bill Taylor. © The Isamu Noguchi Foundation and Garden Museum, New York / Artists Rights Society (ARS), New York.

into a contemporary artistic path.”⁴³

This vision aligns profoundly with Noguchi's desire to make art a space for life. Both artists conceive of art as a purified zone—a field where spirit reenters the world through form.

Even Western critics recognized this depth in Chinese art. Though Clement Greenberg often subordinated Asian aesthetics to his modernist narrative, he still acknowledged Chinese painting's “psychological refinement” and its unmatched sensitivity of brushwork: “That use which conveys exact feeling with every touch and harmonizes each touch, as an individual facet of feeling, with the unifying emotion of the whole picture—the Chinese masters certainly have no equals.”⁴⁴ Similarly, Max Loehr observed that by the Ming dynasty, Chinese painting had become “no longer painting pure and simple but a kind of humanistic discipline, an art blended with learning”—increasingly abstract, allusive, and philosophical.⁴⁵

Zhang's work stands in precisely this lineage: a continuation of the literati ideal that merges technique, reflection, and self-cultivation, now translated into a global visual language.

Yet the differences between Zhang and Noguchi are crucial. Noguchi's vision is rooted in physical space—requiring bodily movement, light, and the viewer's presence. Zhang's *Chengxiang*, by contrast, operates within pictorial space: it evokes place through ink and void, guiding the viewer into an inner topography of thought. In classical Chinese aesthetics, space is not an external container but a projection of the clarified mind (*chenghuai* 澄懷). Thus, while Noguchi builds spaces for the body, Zhang paints spaces for the spirit.

In this comparison, Zhang's *Chengxiang* emerges as part of a trans-media continuity: whether through landscape design or ink painting, art seeks to construct a “purified space” where the human mind can return to its source. Zhang's singular contribution lies in his translation of this universal aspiration into the contemporary language of ink—extending Chinese tradition into the global discourse of abstraction, spirituality, and space.

4. Conclusion

In tracing Lixiang Zhang's *Chengxiang* (澄象) series, this study has situated his art within the broader discourse of abstraction, tradition, and the quest for a spiritual language in contemporary art. Unlike the Western modernist trajectory that often defines itself through rupture and negation, Zhang's practice unfolds

through continuity and transformation. Ink painting, Daoist cosmology, and the literati ideal of self-cultivation are not relics of the past, but living frameworks through which he reimagines modern abstraction as a metaphysical act of renewal. His art demonstrates that Chinese modernity can emerge not through rejection, but through the re-enchantment of inherited forms.

The comparison with Mark Rothko reveals both resonance and divergence. Both artists seek transcendence through color, form, and atmosphere; yet Rothko's “Abstract Sublime,” rooted in the existential condition of postwar Western thought, evokes emotional intensity and metaphysical tension, whereas Zhang's *Chengxiang* transforms the sublime into serenity—an equilibrium that echoes the Chinese aesthetic notion of *jingjie* (artistic realm). Likewise, his dialogue with Isamu Noguchi underscores a shared concern for space as a vessel of contemplation. However, while Noguchi shaped physical landscapes for bodily encounter, Zhang constructs a pictorial sanctuary where brush, void, and tonal gradation interweave as an inner landscape of the mind.

Through these comparative perspectives, Zhang's *Chengxiang* emerges not as a mere stylistic evolution of ink painting, nor as a derivative abstraction, but as a philosophical proposition—an attempt to forge a new sublime that is both globally conversant and locally grounded. His art embodies a disciplined luminosity, where technical precision and spiritual introspection converge to create a universal language of mindfulness. In Zhang's hands, abstraction ceases to be a Western invention and becomes a shared grammar of spiritual inquiry, a means of reconciling difference without erasing identity.

Ultimately, *Chengxiang* invites us to reconsider abstraction itself—not as an escape from the world, but as a return to clarity. In its quiet radiance, painting becomes a site of presence and illumination, where the visible and invisible meet, and where the mind, purified and still, beholds its own reflection.

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Editor: Yao Xiao

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